

Calculation of Strength of Reinforced Concrete Beams with Steel Fibers

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***Abstract:** This scientific article.. presents. the. results. of the theoretical. calculation of the strength. of reinforced. concrete beams dispersed. with steel. fibers.. According. to the results. of calculations., it was found that the strength of fiber-reinforced concrete. beams reinforced with steel fibers. is higher than. the strength. of ordinary. reinforced. concrete beams.*

***Key words:** strength, reinforced concrete, beam, steel fiber, flexure, strength, dispersed reinforcement.*

Introduction

Concrete is one of the most widely used and essential building materials. Concrete is made of cement, water, fine and coarse aggregates, and numerous additives. Concrete strength, is primarily determined by the water-to-cement ratio. Physical and mechanical properties of concrete can be changed by adding different amounts of additives[1, 2].

Concrete has a high compressive strength but poor tensile strength. Concrete is used as a building material when mixed with high-tensile-strength elements. The most frequent way to strengthen concrete is via steel rebars. In reinforced concrete constructions, the concrete interacts with the steel, and the concrete and rebar take compressive and tensile loads simultaneously. Concrete is prone to brittle failure, which usually occurs quickly and unexpectedly. Some of the structures subjected to the bending moment compress, while others extend. Because concrete has a low tensile strength, steel rebars are used in the tensile portion of the construction[3, 4, 5].

In addition, several types of steel and composite fibers can be used to improve the physical and mechanical qualities of concrete. At the same time, the amount of fiber in concrete, its geometry, density, modulus of elasticity, and other mechanical properties of the material all have a significant impact on concrete strength indicators. The addition of various additives to fiber concrete can considerably improve the quality of the finished composite material.

In the theoretical calculation of fiber-reinforced concrete beams dispersedly reinforced with steel fibers, a section normal to the longitudinal axis was carried out.

Calculation, of the strength, of reinforced, concrete and fiber, reinforced concrete, beams is carried, out on the basis, of the following, condition[6].

$$M \leq M_{ult} \tag{1}$$

where: M-bending, moment, generated, by external, loading; M is the limiting, bending, moment, that the section, of the element can take [6].

When calculating, the strength, of reinforced, concrete and fiber,-reinforced concrete, beams., the load, diagram and stress, diagram, in the normal, cross-section relative, to the longitudinal, axis are, shown, in Figure 1.

Fig 1. load, diagram and stress, diagram in the normal, cross-section, relative to the, longitudinal, axis when, calculating, the strength, of a flexible, fiber concrete, element[6]

The value, of the maximum, load-bearing, capacity, M_{ult} of rectangular, fiber, reinforced, concrete, beams, is calculated, based on the following, formula, [6]:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n M = 0$$

$$M_{ult} + R_{fb3} \cdot b \cdot (h - x) \cdot \left(\frac{h - x}{2} - a\right) - R_{sc} \cdot A_s' (h_0 - a') - R_{fb} \cdot b \cdot x \cdot (h_0 - 0,5x) = 0$$

$$M_{ult} = R_{fb} \cdot b \cdot x \cdot (h_0 - 0,5x) - R_{fb3} \cdot b \cdot (h - x) \cdot \left(\frac{h - x}{2} - a\right) + R_{sc} \cdot A_s' (h_0 - a') \tag{2}$$

In this, case., the height, of the compressive, zone of fiber, -reinforced, . concrete, beams, dispersed, reinforced, with steel, fibers, is calculated, by the following, formula, [6] .:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n F_{kv} = 0$$

$$R_s \cdot A_s + R_{fb3} \cdot b(h - x) - R_{sc} \cdot A_s' - R_{fb} \cdot bx = 0$$

$$x = \frac{R_s \cdot A_s - R_{sc} \cdot A_s' + R_{fb3} \cdot b \cdot h}{(R_{fb} + R_{fb3}) \cdot b} \tag{3}$$

According, to the results, of the theoretical, . calculation, . of the beams, ., the load, bearing, capacity, of the reinforced, concrete, beams made, of conventional, . concrete was 88.57, kN.

The load-bearing capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams dispersed reinforced with steel fibers with a content of 1.0% in concrete and a length of 10 mm was 103.60 kN. The load-bearing capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams increased by 16.96% compared to the load-bearing capacity of ordinary reinforced concrete beams. The load-bearing capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams was 108.17 kN, when reinforced by adding 2.0% steel fibers to concrete, with a length of 10 mm. Compared to the load-bearing capacity of reinforced concrete beams made without adding steel fibers, the load-bearing capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams dispersed with steel fibers increased by 22.12%.

The load-bearing capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams dispersed reinforced with steel fibers with a content of 3.0% in concrete and a length of 10 mm was 112.28 kN. The load-bearing capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams increased by 26.76% compared to the load-carrying capacity of ordinary reinforced concrete beams.

The load-bearing capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams with a content of 1.0% of steel fibers and a length of 30 mm is 102.51 kN, when the content of fibers is 2.0%, the load-carrying capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams is 110.52 kN, when the content of fibers is 3.0%, the load-carrying capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams is 105.66 kN. In this case, it was found that the load-carrying capacity of fiber-reinforced concrete beams dispersed with steel fibers increased by 15-25% compared to the load-carrying capacity of ordinary beams.

Fig 1. Bending moment graph

Conclusion

1. According to the results of theoretical calculations, it was found that the load-bearing capacity, that is, the strength of fiber-reinforced concrete beams is higher than the load-bearing capacity of reinforced concrete beams made of ordinary concrete.
2. It was found that the load-bearing capacity of reinforced concrete beams dispersed with steel fibers increased by 15-25% compared to the load-bearing capacity of reinforced concrete beams made of ordinary concrete.

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